

Polyolefin-coated urea as a fertilizer for rice on soil with high nitrogen leaching loss

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Rice farmers in the inland valleys (IVs) of sub-Saharan Africa cultivate under rainfed conditions with little or no bunding. Their fields often alternate between being in flooded and droughty conditions, thus subjecting added inputs, especially N, to leaching and surface runoff. Unfortunately, soil nutrient status in most IVs is very poor and soil is sandy, invariably lowering the efficiency of commonly available N fertilizers, such as urea, and consequently decreasing the yields of improved varieties. Attaining reasonable yields of about 3 t ha⁻¹ requires two to three split applications at 90 kg N ha⁻¹. Farmers do not often attain these yields. Our trial was aimed at finding out the efficiency of polyolefin-coated urea as an alternate N source, with one basal application at 60 kg N ha⁻¹ in sandy soil under poor water management.

A greenhouse study with 54 Wagner pots (500 cm³) was conducted from June to October 1997 and June to October 1998 in Shimane, western Japan. The soil was an Entisol—sandy (91%) and nutritionally poor. Total N was 0.43 g kg⁻¹, total C was 7.46 g kg⁻¹, CEC was 5.35 cmol (+) kg⁻¹, and pH was 5.6. The trial was a randomized complete block design with two factors (fertilizer and water management) and three replications. Fertilizer treatments consisted of (1) no N (N₀), (2) prilled urea at 60 kg N ha⁻¹ applied in two splits—basal and 35 d after transplanting (DAT) (N_x), and (3) polyolefin-coated urea (POCU) at 60 kg N ha⁻¹ applied once basally. Water management was either (1) good water management (GWM)—i.e., submergence throughout the growing season, with periodic water sampling made fortnightly, or (2) poor water management (PWM), with periodic flooding to induce leaching in 1997 and leaching plus surface runoff in 1998. Pots with PWM had their bottom

drainage hole unplugged at 33 DAT in 1997; in 1998, four additional side holes (10-mm diameter) were made. Side holes were unplugged at 14 DAT and the bottom drain hole was unplugged at 25 DAT. GWM pots were not leached, except during water sampling and for mid-season drainage for 24 h. In 1997, 4,500 mm of irrigation water was used in 123 d per pot for PWM; in 1998, 4,200 mm was used in 121 d. The N₀ treatment with GWM had 320 mm and 400 mm of irrigation in 1997 and 1998, respectively. POCU and urea, on the other hand, had 600 mm and 760 mm of irrigation in 1997 and 1998, respectively, to maintain submerged conditions during the growing season.

Thirty-day-old seedlings (cv. IR36) were transplanted. Each pot had two hills with two seedlings per hill. All pots received a basal application of 13.2 kg P ha⁻¹ as calcium phosphate and 24.9 kg K ha⁻¹ as muriate of potash. Two slow-release POCU fertilizers, LPS40 and LPS100, were used in both years. In 1997, LPS100 was used alone; in 1998, a 1:1 combination of LP40 and LPS100 was used. LPS100 belongs to the delayed-release group and has a

sigmoid-shaped release pattern. It is released very slowly in the first 40 d of application. In water at 25 °C, 80% of the N is released in 100 d. LP40, on the other hand, belongs to the ordinary-release group with a linear release pattern. Yield data were corrected to 14% moisture content.

Results showed that mean grain yield and number of grains per panicle were higher in 1997 than in 1998, whereas productive tiller number and 1,000-grain weight were similar in both years (Tables 1 and 2). In 1997, the urea treatment produced yield not significantly different from the POCU treatment under GWM, but the POCU treatment was significantly higher (378 g m⁻²) than the urea treatment (316 g m⁻²) under PWM. Under GWM, the POCU treatment had significantly more grains. In 1998, the grain yields of both the POCU and urea treatments were comparable under GWM. However, the POCU treatment under PWM yielded significantly higher (343 g m⁻²) than the urea treatment (261 g m⁻²). The number of grains per panicle of the POCU treatment under both water management regimes was significantly higher than that

Table 1. Mean grain yield, yield component, PFP, and ANUE for 1997.

Treatment	Tillers pot ⁻¹ (no.)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (g m ⁻²)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	PFP ^a (kg kg ⁻¹ N)	ANUE ^b (kg kg ⁻¹ N)
<i>Good water management</i>						
No N	4.7	22	103	74.2	—	—
POCU ^c	10.3	22	401	115.6	66.9	49.7
Urea	13.7	23	411	71.8	68.5	51.3
5% LSD ^d	1.6 ^e		52 ns	29.2 ^e	7.3 ns	11.7 ns
<i>Poor water management</i>						
No N	7.4	22	156	68.3	—	—
POCU ^c	12.9	21	378	100.1	62.9	36.9
Urea	12.5	22	316	71.2	52.8	26.8
5% LSD ^d	1.6 ns		52 ^e	29.2 ns	7.3 ^e	11.7 ns

^aPFP (partial factor productivity) = Yield/N_x. ^bANUE (agronomic nitrogen-use efficiency) = (yield at N_x - yield at N₀)/applied N at N_x. ^cPOCU is a controlled-release fertilizer; in 1997, LPS100 was used. ^dLSD is a comparison between POCU and prilled urea. In 1997, POCU was LPS100. ^e = significant at P = 0.05. ns = not significant.

Table 2. Mean grain yield, yield components, PFP, and ANUE for 1998.

Treatment	Tillers pot ⁻¹ (no.)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (g m ⁻²)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	PFP ^a (kg kg ⁻¹ N)	ANUE ^b (kg kg ⁻¹ N)
<i>Good water management</i>						
No N	5.2	21	111	60.0	—	—
POCU ^c	11.8	23	354	77.5	59.0	40.5
Urea	14.3	23	330	57.7	54.9	36.5
5% LSD ^d	2.1 ^e		44 ns	14.1 ^e	4.6 ns	12.8 ns
<i>Poor water management</i>						
No N	7.8	21	133	47.1	—	—
POCU ^c	13.3	21	343	71.6	57.2	35.0
Urea	12.8	21	261	57.1	43.4	21.2
5% LSD ^d	2.1 ns		44 ^e	14.1 ^e	4.6 ^e	12.8 ^e

^aPFP (partial factor productivity) = Yield/N_x. ^bANUE (agronomic nitrogen-use efficiency) = (Yield at N_x - yield at N₀)/applied N at N_x. ^cPOCU is a controlled-release fertilizer; in 1998, the combination of LP40 and LPS100 was 1:1. ^dLSD is a comparison between POCU and prilled urea. ^e = significant at P = 0.05. ns = not significant.

under the urea treatment (Table 2). The POCU treatment performed significantly better than prilled urea, either with leaching alone or with a combination of

leaching and surface runoff. This can be attributed to the slow-release pattern of N, which matches the need of the plant,

consequently giving POCU more grains per panicle.

In 1997, partial factor productivity (PFP)—but not agronomic nitrogen-use efficiency (ANUE)—of the POCU treatment under PWM was significantly higher than that of the urea treatment. However, in 1998, both PFP and ANUE of the POCU treatment were significantly higher than those of the urea treatment. This implies that the slow-release mechanism of polyolefin-coated urea enhances N-use efficiency of the plant. This better performance of POCU under PWM indicates a potential for increased rice yield if POCU is basally applied at 60 kg N ha⁻¹ to nutritionally poor soil with high N leaching loss.

Nitrogen source and application time before flooding affect rice yield in Spain

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Valencian rice growers usually apply excess N, which results in loss of soil quality because of its negative effects on the soil N₂-fixing cyanobacteria (Carreres et al 1996). In Valencia, constraints in the irrigation system have led to lack of control in water management, with difficulties in irrigating after incorporating N fertilizer. The low N efficiency reflects substantial N losses (Fernández Valiente et al 2000). Improving N efficiency and soil use by preserving and developing the ability of N₂-fixing organisms for biofertilization would reduce N fertilizer use and result in ecological, economic, and environmental benefits. N efficiency cannot be improved by split application in Valencia (Carreres et al 1998) but it can be enhanced by slow-release fertilizers (SRF) in Europe (Moletti et al 1989). The relationships between N₂ fixation, physical and chemical characteristics of water and sediments, and rates and

timing of inorganic N fertilizers were described in previous papers (Quesada et al 1997, Carreres et al 1998). Studies dealing with the effect of SRF on N₂ fixation are lacking. This work evaluates the use of different SRF and nitrification inhibitors (NI) in rice fields of Valencia, Spain.

Experiments were conducted during 1998-99 at the Rice Department in Valencia, Spain. Eight N sources (ammonium sulfate [AS], urea, polymer-coated urea [PCU, 32% and 40% N], sulfur-coated urea [MSCU], isobutylidene diurea [IBDU], N ammoniacal form [AF] + dicyandiamide [DCD, 11:1], and AF + dimethyl pyrazolo phosphate [DMPP, 11:1], including a control [no N] were applied at 120 kg N ha⁻¹ and at 2 or 15 d before flooding (DBF) during 1998. Four N sources (urea blended with PCU [40% N] at four ratios: 1:0, 3:1, 1:1, 1:3) were applied at four rates (70, 95, 120, and 145

kg N ha⁻¹) and at 15 DBF during 1999.

Treatment plots, each replicated four times, were laid out in a split-plot design (delay in flooding after N application as main plot and N source as subplot) during 1998 and in a randomized block design in 1999. N fertilizer was given as a single broadcast application. After flooding, seeds were broadcast at 180 kg ha⁻¹.

In June and July 1998, *in situ* acetylene-reducing activity (ARA) was measured only in plots where fertilizer was applied 2 DBF (see table). At crop maturity, grain and straw yields and N content in plants were determined (Carreres et al 1996). In 1998, traits were subjected to a split-plot analysis of variance (N source and timing) and in 1999 to a one-way (no N and 16 treatments: four N sources at four N rates) and a split-plot (N rates as main plot and N source as subplot) analysis of variance.